

IMPROVEMENT OF JIZZAKH CITY WASTEWATER TREATMENT PLANT OPERATION

Ilana Jessica Porter

, University of California, Berkeley.

e-mail: ilanap@stanford.edu

U.M.Qutlimurodov

, Associate professor JizPI, Jizzakh, Republic of Uzbekistan.

e-mail: ulugb002@gmail.com

Abstract: On 12.11.2015 a "Loan Agreement" was signed between the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Loan 3275-UZB) and the Asian Development Bank (ADB) for the implementation of the "Development of Sewerage System in Jizzakh City" project. The above-mentioned project will provide improved wastewater services to 85,000 people in the city of Jizzakh, as well as the nearby district center Uchtepa, and will create conditions for improving the environment, public health and expanding opportunities for socio-economic development of the region. As part of the loan agreement in 2018-2023, construction and installation work for the wastewater treatment plant was performed in the Sh. Rashidovsky district and the Uchtepa plant was commissioned in January 2023. This project also provides for the construction of 53.5 km of sewer networks, cleaning the existing 9.5 km sewer network and reconstruction of 3 existing sewage pumping stations in the city.

This article presents the results of scientific research on the analysis of wastewater discharged by industrial enterprises in Jizzakh and presents scientific and technical proposals, having an innovative nature on the problems of their solutions that currently arise in the work of the wastewater treatment plant. For the uninterrupted and normal use of the capacity of the treatment plant, it is necessary to bring the composition of wastewater discharged by all enterprises of the city into line with the standards.

Introduction: The object of the study is the wastewater treatment plant "Uchtepa", designed to treat wastewater from the whole city of Jizzakh, with a capacity of 30,000 m³ per day, at a construction cost of USD 101,480,000. In practice, the main problem with the new wastewater treatment plant is that the criteria for the composition of wastewater discharged by industrial enterprises in the city do not meet the design standards for treatment coming to the wastewater treatment plant.

Many researchers, including A.B. Adelshin, A.S. Selugin, A.V. Busarev, N.S. Urmitova, L.R. Hisameyeva, E.S. Buriev, A.N. Gadaev, S.S. Sayriddinov and others participated in the research to study the problems of wastewater treatment plant. According to the literature review, there are no data and calculations to study the problems arising from the incorrect operation of the existing sewage systems and wastewater treatment plant in Jizzakh city.

Methods: In carrying out this work, materials of the project of development of the system of construction of new sewerage networks and wastewater treatment plant of Jizzakh city were used. To solve the problems of

uninterrupted and normal use of sewer networks and wastewater treatment plant, a structural analysis of the composition of wastewater from industrial enterprises entering the city collector.

Results and discussion: In accordance with the Presidential Decree of 30.11.2018 № PP-4040 "On additional measures for the development of drinking water supply and sanitation systems in the Republic of Uzbekistan" works are carried out, which will be listed below and are under development. Jizzakh oblast is located in the central part of Uzbekistan between the Syrdarya and Zarafshan rivers. The area of the province is 21.2 thousand km² [1,2]. Most of this area is semi-desert, part of which is developed and as irrigated land is used for agriculture. The climate of Jizzakh is sharply continental with cold winters and hot summers. One of the important goals of the leadership of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to provide the population with clean drinking water and sanitary conditions. As a result, untreated wastewater has been discharged into the environment for more than 15 years. This is an acute problem in most second-tier cities, such as Jizzakh, where more than 230,000 people currently live, of which only about 40% of homes are connected to the sewage system [3,4]. Given the current situation, it was necessary to build new sewage treatment plants and related facilities, such as new pumping stations and sewage system networks.

In order to solve the set tasks on 12.11.2015 was signed "Loan Agreement" between the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Loan 3275-UZB) and the Asian Development Bank (ADB) on the implementation of the project "Development of the sewage system in Jizzakh". "KOMMUNHIZMAT" Agency was approved as the executive agency for the implementation of the project, and later, from 2020, "UZSUVTA'MINOT" JSC. And the implementation agency, i.e. the direct customer, was appointed State Unitary Enterprise "SUVOKOVA", later on, "SUV TA'MINOT" JOINT STOCK COMPANY "JIZZAX SUV TA'MINOTI" LLO of Jizzakh Province (water supply and sewage enterprise), which is responsible for managing the project activities [5,6]. The above-mentioned project will provide improved wastewater services to 85,000 people in the city of Jizzakh, as well as the nearby Uchtepa district, and will create conditions to improve the environment, public health and expand opportunities for socio-economic development of the region. The project "Development of the sewerage system in the city of Jizzakh" includes three major construction lots:

- construction of new sewage treatment facilities in Jizzakh city;
- construction and rehabilitation of sewage collectors and networks with a length of 63 km, including the construction of additional 53.5 km of sewage networks and cleaning of existing sewage networks with a length of 9.5 km.
- reconstruction of the existing 3 sewage pumping stations, which includes the following facilities which includes the following facilities:
 - reconstruction of the pumping station Zilol with a capacity of 90 m³/h;
 - reconstruction of the H. Nosirov pumping station with a capacity of 90 m³/h;

- reconstruction of the Uchtepa pumping station with a capacity of 140 m³/h.
The treatment plant is located on an area of 30 hectares of low-yielding agricultural land (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. New scheme of the sewage network of the city of Jizzakh

Wastewater comes from a city collector with a diameter of 800 mm and after all stages of treatment are discharged into the canal for sewage disposal "Ulgursay" (Fig. 2). The main problem today is that there are some issues that prevent the full and effective functioning of the above-mentioned project:

1. Some industrial enterprises located in Jizzakh city do not have their own local wastewater treatment facilities;

2. Enterprises with their own local treatment facilities discharge wastewater into the city's sewage system without treating it according to established standards.

3. Some companies lack the necessary technology to adequately treat wastewater before it is discharged into the city's sewers.

There are 22 commercial and industrial enterprises in the city that plan to discharge process wastewater from the production process into the new sewer system [7,8]. In accordance with the Decree of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan № 11 dated 03.02.2010 (Installations № 1), industrial enterprises must carry out pre-treatment of process wastewater in order to meet the following established norms and standards:

- discharge of industrial wastewater, the flow and composition of which may result in exceeding the amount and quantity of pollutants allowed by the established standards entering the water body;
- industrial wastewater with a temperature above 40°S;
- pH below 6.5 or above 9;
- chemical oxygen demand (COD) level higher than the biological oxygen

- demand (BOD-5) by more than 2.5 times or BOD full by more than 1.5 times - not exceeding 500 mg/l;
- suspended and floating substances in concentrations exceeding 500 mg/l.

Figure 3. Control point of the wastewater treatment plant "Uchtepa"

- substances for which there are no MPD limits in the sewage network: acids, hot impurities, toxic and dissolved gaseous substances, in particular, solvents (gasoline, diethyl ether, dichloromethane, benzene, etc.), dyes capable of forming toxic gases (hydrogen sulfide, carbon disulfide, carbon monoxide, hydrogen cyanide, volatile aromatic hydrocarbons vapor, etc.) in sewage networks and treatment facilities.) and other explosive and fire-hazardous, toxic mixtures, concentrated mother liquors and goblets, and wastewater containing radioactive substances [9,10].

In addition, the decree provides for monthly reporting of industrial enterprises on the analysis of the composition of technological wastewater to the LLC "SUVTA'MINOT" and the offices of the "GOSKOMPRIRODA" of the regions on a monthly basis [11,12]. In the places of discharge into the sewer system of the city of the wastewater of enterprises, there shall be installed shut-off valves, by means of which there is a possibility to disconnect the enterprise that does not meet the established requirements. Also, each enterprise must have a water measuring device, by which the actual wastewater discharged is measured and recorded. In January 2023, we, together with LLC "SUVTA'MINOT" and the Department of "Goskompriroda" region were taken samples of industrial wastewater from 8 appropriate facilities of industrial enterprises and laboratory analysis of their compositions (Table 1). At present, all 8 enterprises discharge wastewater into the collectors either without treatment at all, or without sufficient treatment, which go to the new treatment plant. The results of analyses show that the composition of wastewater does not meet the established norms and standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan, even at those enterprises that have local treatment facilities [13,14]. The results confirm the need for industrial enterprises to address the following issues:

- install local sewage treatment plants; enterprises that do not have them;
- to reconstruct or overhaul existing sewage treatment plants;
- to strictly comply with the requirements of the Government Decree № 11

of 03.02.2010.

Consider the results of wastewater analysis on the example of LLO "Master Building", which produces metal screws.

The results of chemical analysis of wastewater discharged from the sewerage networks of Jizzakh city

Table 1

№	Ingredients	Unit measurement	Standard	Wastewater sampling point 2023 Jan.							
				Jizzakh grains	Battery Factory	Toshtepa textile	Jizzakh sifat broiler	Eco Climate	Master Building LLO	Sofitel paint factory	Jizzakh Testil
1	pH		6,5-8,5	6,9	7	6,8	7,4	7,3	7,02	8	7,2
2	ChOD	mg/l	160-220	600	800	600	400	300	280	400	280
3	BOD-5	mg/l	15-20	30	40	36	30	30	40	40	25
4	NH ₄ -ammonia	mg/l	1	8	12	20	12	6	5	20	18
5	NO ₂ -nitrites	mg/l	0,2	0,05	0,07	0,03	0,07	0,08	0,09	0,4	0,09
6	NO ₃ -nitrates	mg/l	9,1	28	30	12	20	30	24	30	30
7	Suspended matter	mg/l	150	350	300	200	600	300	700	500	300
8	SO ₄ -sulfates	mg/l	100	380	800	500	300	300	280	280	240
9	ChL-chlorides	mg/l	350	540	700	2800	200	500	220	2200	75
10	Mineralization	ekv/l	2000	2400	3000	3200	2200	2600	1500	3000	880
11	Oil Products	mg/l	1	0,1	0,2	0,5	1	0,4	2	0,5	0,4
12	Fe-ferrume	mg/l	0,03	0,03	0,1	0,05	0,04	0,05	0,08	0,08	0,05

Having analyzed the results of the composition of wastewater of this enterprise, given in Table 2, it was found that the concentration of ChOD, BOD, ammonia, nitrates, suspended solids, sulfates, petroleum products and iron significantly exceed the approved normative indicators.

Results of wastewater analysis by Master Building LLO

Table 2

№	Ingredients	Unit measurement	Sample 2023 Jan.	
			Standard	Master Building LLO
1	pH	mg/l	6.5 - 8.5	7,02
2	ChOD	mg/l	160-220	280
3	BOD-5	mg/l	15-20	40
4	NH ₄ -ammonia	mg/l	1	5
5	NO ₂ -nitrites	mg/l	0,2	0,09
6	NO ₃ -nitrates	mg/l	9,1	24
7	Suspended matter	mg/l	150	700
8	SO ₄ -sulfates	mg/l	100	280

9	CL-chlorides	ekv/l	350	220
10	Mineralization	mg/l	2000	1500
11	Oil Products	mg/l	1	2
12	Fe-ferrume		0,03	0,08

According to the production technology of metal screws, the screws made from metal wire have a temperature of 180-200 °S. To cool them down, they are dipped in flammable oil and then washed with hot water. As a result of washing, hot waste water with petroleum products and small metal particles is formed. This waste water is conveyed to the settling tank, where the water and the flammable oil separate and the metal particles settle to the bottom. The oil on the surface of the water is withdrawn manually and discharged into separate containers. And cleaning the settling tank from metal sludge is impossible without stopping the entire technological process[15-20]. With this wastewater treatment technology, some of the oil and metal particles are discharged into the city sewage system, from where they get to the treatment plant "Uchtepa". The detected situation on the part of "SUVTA'MINOT" LLC, and the Department of "GOSKOMPRIRODA" of the region leads to the imposition of penalties to the enterprise for failure to comply with established norms.

In order to improve the technology of treatment of generated waste water between the enterprise LLO "Master Building" and Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute entered into a contract to develop the technology of treatment of generated waste water. To solve this problem the scientists of the institute proposed the project technology of wastewater treatment with the help of high-gradient magnetic separators. The working elements of magnetic separators are in the form of cylinders and rods. A liquid flows through them in the transverse direction. To increase the efficiency of cleaning from ferromagnetic particles, traditionally one tries to increase the gradient and induction of the magnetic field by upgrading the working The magnetic field configuration and modernizing the working area. The proposed magnetic separator devices are adapted to specific operating conditions and are capable of extracting ferromagnetic particles with a certain magnetic moment. Nanodispersed magnetite creates a small volume fraction of ferromagnetic material on the surface of an oil globule, so its

extraction requires a high-energy magnetic system, with satisfying such the magnetic field gradient and induction parameters are required to meet such requirements.

Figure 4. Drum magnetic separator-BC 25/340 with capacity: 0.5 - 3 m³/h

Figure 5. Scheme of operation of magnetic separators installation

- 1,2. Magnetic separator;
3. Tank;
4. Reservoir of magnetite-oil mixture after washing;
5. Washing line;
6. Purified liquid line;
7. Tray for drying and roasting of magnetite;
8. Magnet;

9. Furnace;
10. Wash fluid inlet line;
11. Pump;
12. Water inlet line from the tank;

When using the proposed technology, the following results can be obtained:

1. Daily purification of wastewater with separation of flammable oil up to 500 liters from water and metal particles, with the possibility of reuse.
2. separation of metal particles from waste water without stopping the technological process and their use as secondary raw materials.
3. When using the proposed technology, the regulatory requirements for the degree of purification of wastewater discharged into the city sewage system are satisfied.

CONCLUSIONS:

Scientific research on the analysis of wastewater discharged by industrial enterprises of Djizak city into the city sewerage network has been conducted and cases of non-compliance of their composition The cases of non-compliance of their composition with the established normative requirements were revealed.

On the example of LLC "Master Building" studied the used technology of wastewater treatment and proposed the technology of wastewater treatment using high-gradient magnetic separators. The application of this technology achieves standard indicators of wastewater treatment, with the possibility of discharge into the municipal sewer system.

It is necessary to study and conduct scientific research to develop technologies for the treatment of wastewater from other industrial enterprises and bring their composition to the established regulatory requirements.

It is necessary to improve the wastewater treatment technology of the remaining enterprises, discharging the generated process water without sufficient treatment. Only this way it is possible to achieve a degree of water purification that meets the established criteria and ensure the smooth operation of the municipal wastewater treatment plant "Uchtepa".

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